
EVALUATION OF DEEP LEARNING FOR THE DIAGNOSIS OF LEUKEMIA BLOOD CANCER

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ABSTRACT

One of the crucial challenges in disease diagnostics is the timely identification of leukemia, primarily the distinction between various malignant leukocytes in an initial stage of an illness. The DL model, which is used to diagnose leukemia, a blood malignancy, is the main focus of this work. This specific research aims to evaluate the feasibility of deep learning approach to that of Leukemia detection from blood smear images used in the C-NMC 2019 dataset. For the next stage, the C-NMC 2019 dataset that was collected from Kaggle were pre-processed. It also involved uses like transforms in the converted data into RGB colour and then there is a method called resize on the data. After that, a dataset was divided again into two parts, which are the preferred training set and the preferred testing set. There was clear evidence that different classification models existed which was used in the diagnosis process. The models that were used were RestNet50, Neighborhood-Correction Algorithm and EfficientNetV2S. The assessment metrics that were utilized included F1-score, recall, accuracy, and precision. After performing a comparative study, it was determined that EfficientNetV2S was the most accurate model, as it achieved a score of 99.73% for correctness. In the future, research could explore innovative architectures, optimize preprocessing approaches, and increase datasets to improve generalization and clinical relevance. Additionally, interpretability may be investigated in order to improve medical image analysis.

Keywords: Acute Leukemia, Blood Cancer, Deep Learning, Machine Learning, Efficientnetv2s, White Blood Cells

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1. INTRODUCTION

The WHO estimates that around 19 million individuals will get a cancer diagnosis. Ten million patients perished as a result. The aggressive nature of cancer and the difficulty and expense of treating it make it the leading cause of mortality worldwide. How a cancer patient is treated is conditional on the specific cancer kind. A disorder that affects the blood cells is called leukemia. The human body's cells depend on blood to provide them with nutrition and oxygen. Moreover, it removes the garbage that is generated by them. The existence of two distinct types of leukemia has been established: acute and chronic. Since it spreads quickly and has more excruciating symptoms than the second kind, the acute form is the most deadly and aggressive. The most prevalent kinds impact adults and children, respectively, and are called acute myelogenous leukemia (AML) and acute lymphocytic leukemia (ALL). ALL has an impact on leukemic cells. This phenomenon produces an excessive amount of differences in the white blood cells [1]. The majority of identified recorded instances of ALL occur before the age of six, with children among the ages of three and seven being most vulnerable. According to the WHO, leukemia is the main cause of the high cancer mortality rates. Leukemia that is acute develops faster than that of chronic leukemia. In acute leukemia, the majority of cells are unable to carry out their usual tasks; in chronic leukemia, some cells are immature but the majority of cells are functioning normally. There is a longer window for discovery, but the issue grows more serious as time passes. It is of the utmost importance to identify instances of acute leukemia promptly.

Vertebrate immune systems rely on lymphocytes, a specific kind of white blood cell. Lymphocytes may be visually classified into two groups: tiny lymphocytes and big and granular lymphocytes. A substantial majority of lymphocytes are identical to natural killer cells. Both T cells and B cells make up small lymphocytes. In contrast to B cells, which make antibodies and use them to combat foreign cells, T cells attack and defend themselves. The genetic code dictates the fate of these cells. This phase does not progress in a leukaemia patient, and the conversion does not take place. Leukaemia is characterized by a 20% increase in blast cells in the peripheral circulation.

Figure 1: Normal blood vs leukemia blood cells

Researchers, doctors, and hematologists have long struggled with the problem of early leukemia diagnosis. Leukemia symptoms include enlarged lymph nodes, pale skin, fever, and loss of weight; however, these signs and symptoms may be caused by other conditions as well. The modest signs of early-stage leukemia make diagnosis challenging. Leukemia is most often diagnosed by microscopic examination of PBS, while the gold standard for the diagnosis of leukemia is to collect and analyze bone marrow samples [2].

Laboratory image analysis using DL and computer-aided diagnostic methods has been employed in many studies over the last 20 years to try to solve the problems associated with delayed leukemia diagnosis and to identify its subtypes. The blood smear pictures have been analyzed in this research in order to count the cells in different forms of leukemia and to diagnose the disease.

A. Contribution of the study

There are numerous contributions that this study provides to the domain of diagnosis of leukemia and blood cancer. The following is a summary of this study's main contribution:

- Begin by extracting the data from the dataset called the C-NMC 2019 dataset.
- Subsequently, data preparation was conducted, including, Transformed into an RGB color, data augmentation and Feature extraction.
- A data is splitted into two parts: testing and training.
- Several classification models, have been used in this study.
- Once the assessment of the process model has been completed, recall, f1-score, accuracy, and precision got utilized.
- Lastly, compare all the models to see which one performs at the highest degree of accuracy.

B. Structure of paper

The supplemental parts of the article are structured as follows: In Section 2, the terms leukemia and blood cancer are defined. Section 3 details the procedures and processes. The findings are examined and spoken about in Section 4. Section 5 presents the research's conclusions and recommendations for moving ahead.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section, provide some previous work on diagnosis of leukemia blood cancer based on machine and DL.

In [3] extracted leukemia data from two open-source databases: ALL-IDB and ASH Image Bank. The next step was to enhance the data using seven distinct picture alteration algorithms. To identify all subtypes of leukemia, they used a CNN architecture. In addition, they delved into other popular ML techniques including DT, KNN, NB, and SVM. They used a series of experiments and 5-fold cross-validation to assess our method. Experiment findings shown that our CNN model achieves an accuracy of 88.25% when comparing healthy individuals to those with leukemia, and an accuracy of 81.74% when classifying all subtypes using multiple classes. Lastly, they demonstrated that the CNN model outperforms other popular ML techniques.

In this paper [4] discover leukemia using ML, which may aid medical researchers in determining if a patient has cancer or not. A decision-making mechanism for the leukemia detection system was therefore necessary. Therefore, in order to improve the accuracy of leukemia detection, they provide a few popular techniques in our work. Various ML techniques, such as NB, SVM, DT, and KNN algorithm, were used to determine whether a patient has cancer or not. There are 401 data in our database that originate from Z H Shikder Medical College and Hospital. The DT algorithm outperforms the others and delivers predictions with a perfect track record. This study also includes the findings of comparing several algorithms' precision, recall, and F1 score on all of our data samples.

In [5] created eTumorType, a method for cancer type identification using cancer founding clone copy number variations (CNVs). Computer methods including SGB, voting, centroid, and leading patterns are integrated into eTumorType, which incorporates cancer hallmark principles. There are 5327 tumour samples and 18 major cancer kinds in the big dataset that eTumorType was trained and validated on. With recall rates ranging from 0.79 to 0.92 and accuracies ranging from 0.86-0.96, eTumorType successfully predicted cases of kidney, colon, brain, and prostate malignancies. Also, for the prediction of ovarian, breast luminal, lung, endometrial, stomach, head and neck, leukemia, and skin cancers, decent accuracies (0.78-0.92) and recall rates (0.58-0.95) have been attained. The findings indicate that eTumorType has the potential to be used for non-invasive cancer type determination using CNVs of CTCs and cfDNAs in non-invasive diagnostic procedures.

In [6] investigate the potential of DL for AML prognostic prediction. The research relies on 94 AML patients taken from the Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) database. Age, together with the findings of the ten most frequent cytogenetic and twenty-three most common mutations, are input data; the outcome is the prognosis, or diagnosis to death (DTD). To compress and organise raw data and extract high-level characteristics, our DL network stacks autoencoders to create a hierarchical DL model. The R-coded network can forecast an AML prognosis for a specific patient (defined as a DTD of 730 days or less). With an impressive 83% accuracy rate, the DL network predicts the prognosis. Our early findings show that DL can be used to prognostic prediction utilising next-gene sequencing (NGS) data in the future, which is a proof-of-concept research.

This study [7] evaluate the various prognostic scoring methods. Materials and Methods: The research comprised 101 individuals diagnosed with primary MDS between 2003 and 2011 in the hematology department of a tertiary care university hospital. Results: Leukemia-free survival and overall survival declined ($p < 0.001$) with a rise in the risk categories of the revised IPSS (IPSS-R), WHO Classification-Based Prognostic Scoring System (WPSS), MD Anderson Prognostic Scoring System (MPSS), and International Prognostic Scoring System (IPSS). The WPSS outperformed the other prognostic systems in terms of leukemia-free survival ($p < 0.001$) and overall survival ($p = 0.037$), as determined by a Cox regression analysis comparing the IPSS, WPSS, MPSS, and IPSS-R. Conclusion: The four prognostic algorithms that were tested were all able to accurately forecast both overall survival and survival free of leukemia ($p < 0.001$). Results showed that the WPSS was the most accurate predictor of overall survival and leukemia-free survival in particular, with the IPSS-R and WPSS both ranking well in this regard.

Table 1: a comparative study on the diagnosis of Leukemia Blood Cancer based on deep learning

Ref	Sources	Methodology	Performance	Limitations & Future Work
Ahmed et al., 2019	ALL-IDB, ASH Image Bank	CNN, Naive Bayes, SVM, KNN, Decision Tree	Applied CNN for leukemia subtype classification, compared with other ML algorithms	CNN accuracy: 88.25% (leukemia vs. healthy), 81.74% (multi-class classification); CNN outperformed other models
Das Mou and Kumar Saha, 2019	Z H Shikder Medical College and Hospital	Naive Bayes, SVM, KNN, Decision Tree	Proposed ML system for leukemia detection, comparative analysis of multiple algorithms	Decision Tree achieved 100% accuracy in leukemia detection; analysis of precision, recall, and F1 score for different algorithms
Zou and Wang, 2017	Dataset of 5327 tumor samples including 18 common cancer types	TumorType (Stochastic Gradient Boosting, Voting, Centroid, Leading Patterns)	Developed eTumorType to classify cancer types based on CNVs	Accuracy: 0.86–0.96 (common cancers), 0.78–0.92 (other cancers); recall: 0.79–0.92 (common cancers), 0.58–0.95 (other cancers)
Lin et al., 2018	TCGA (The Cancer Genome Atlas), 94 AMLR cases	Deep Learning (Autoencoders, R)	Used DL to predict the prognosis of acute myeloid leukemia based on cytogenetic and mutation data	Accuracy of 83% for predicting prognosis (DTD of more or less than 730 days); demonstrated practical application of DL in AML prognosis prediction
Bektaş et al., 2016	Tertiary care university hospital, 101 primary MDS patients	IPSS, WPSS, MPSS, IPSS-R (Cox Regression Analysis)	Compared prognostic systems for leukemia-free survival and overall survival prediction	WPSS was the best for predicting leukemia-free survival; WPSS and IPSS-R were better for overall survival predictions

A. Research Gaps

The current models for leukemia detection and prognosis prediction, although promising, frequently rely on restricted datasets and concentrate on specific tasks, such as binary classification or subtype prediction. Due to tiny and non-diverse datasets, comparative studies lack robustness, and many DL models are still in a proof-of-concept stage with little to no clinical validation. The integration of many data types—including imaging, clinical, and genetic data—remains largely unexplored. More generalisable, scalable models that are validated in actual clinical situations are required.

III. METHODOLOGY

The type of work that is used in the given context is described in this part of the play. Within this section, there are a few subsections. It provides information about the dataset and the preprocessing of the data used in the given research.

a. Methodology

The approach employed in this study to diagnose leukemia blood cancer involved multiple steps like data preparation, data acquisition, data transformation, data partitioning, and comparing differential classification algorithms. To start with, the C-NMC 2019 dataset was collected from Kaggle website was utilized for the data-collecting process. Apparently, this dataset provided a lot of valuable information concerning pictures of blood cells. Several preprocessing techniques included converting the photos to RGB color space models where missing values were also rectified a balanced augmented dataset was also used. Other CNN structures that were used for feature extraction include Decision Tree, RestNet152, Finally, EfficientNetV2S. A data was divided into training and testing set for a purpose of assessing the model. Other assessment parameters include F1-score, recall, accuracy, and precision while confusion matrices were used to present the outcome of the assessment.

Figure 2: Data Flow Diagram

The following steps of data flow diagram is detailed description given in below:

1. Data Collection

The word "data collection" describes the steps used to gather information from many sources, analyse it, and then find patterns and potential solutions to problems. This comparative study made use of the C-NMC 2019 dataset, which was gathered via Kaggle and provided valuable insights for analysis.

2. Data Preprocessing

The removal of unwanted data from a dataset is called Preprocessing. The data acquired may contain outliers and absent values that must be eliminated prior to being fed into the model. The following key pre-processing steps is listed below:

- **Transformed into an RGB color:** Several techniques are used to the input blood microscopic images at this point after they have initially been converted into an RGB colour model. They are then adjusted to 227 x 227 in terms of dimensions.

3. Data Augmentation

The issue of a dataset's restricted size may be solved, especially in deep learning issues, by using data augmentation methods. To create several versions of the original image, a number of image augmentation methods are used, including rotation, flipping, and cropping. Training our system with both original and enhanced images increases the algorithm's capacity for generalization.

4. Feature Extraction

The technique of identifying the crucial and relevant facts by grouping all of the data is known as feature extraction [8]. Gathering all the information required or minimizing the loss of pertinent data is essential when dealing with enormous datasets. Feature extraction lowers the risk of data loss by managing the important information from the enormous raw dataset.

5. Data Splitting

Data separation is a common step for training and testing the model. In this study, dataset is split into two parts. The two parts are training and testing.

6. Classification Models

For the comparative analysis use some classification models for diagnosis of leukemia blood cancer are describe in this section.

2. RestNet50

ResNet 50 is a type of deep convolutional network consisting of fifty layers, making it significantly deeper than its predecessor, ResNet 34. ResNet50 uses residual connections, which allows it to overcome the vanishing gradient problem and allows for the training of deeper networks without sacrificing accuracy.

3. Neighborhood-correction algorithm (NCA)

The Neighborhood-Correction Algorithm is a method used in machine learning and data analysis, particularly for enhancing classification performance in high-dimensional datasets. It typically works by correcting the labels or feature values of a sample based on its surrounding neighbors, improving accuracy by leveraging local patterns in the data.

4. Efficient Net

The Efficient Net relies on a ground-breaking approach to scaling CNN models. It relies on a simple yet effective compound coefficient. In contrast to more traditional approaches, Efficient Net uses a set of scaling factors to uniformly scale all dimensions, including network properties such as width, depth, and resolution. Although improving model performance by scaling individual dimensions is possible, achieving resource balance across all network dimensions significantly improves model performance in reality. In order to uniformly scale up the depth, breadth, and resolution of the coefficient, the authors came up with the provided formulae.

$$\text{depth: } d = \alpha\varphi \quad \dots \dots (1)$$

$$\text{width: } w = \beta\varphi \quad \dots \dots (2)$$

$$\text{resolution: } r = \gamma\varphi \quad \dots \dots (3)$$

$$s.t. \alpha \cdot \beta^2 \cdot \gamma^2 \approx 2 \quad \dots \dots (4)$$

$$\alpha \geq 1, \beta \geq 1, \gamma \geq 1 \quad \dots \dots (5)$$

The accessibility of various new resources for model scaling is controlled by the user-specified coefficient φ , while the specific allocation of these additional resources to the network's depth, width, and resolution is determined by the constants α , β , and γ , which can be found through a fast grid search. When it comes to Efficient Net models, MBConv is the backbone. MB Conv is based on model principles from Mobile Net [9].

IV. COMPARATIVE RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section offers an outcome obtained through an evaluation of the dataset used in this study, including the results, description of the dataset, performance metrics, and classifier statistics.

1. Dataset Description

There are 118 participants and 15,114 lymphocyte images in the C-NMC 2019 collection. There are three folders for the images. One set, titled "C-NMC training data," includes 47 individuals' cells (10661 total), 7272 cancer cells, and 33,389 healthy cells. Another set of data, titled "CNMC test preliminary phase data," includes 1867 cells, 1219 cancer cells, and 648 healthy cells drawn from 15 individuals. The last folder, titled "C-NMC test end phase data," has 2586 cells from 17 participants that were not labelled. This collection includes single-cell pictures of normal and malignant cells that have previously been recognized by skilled oncologists.

Figure 3: Sample of the dataset

1. Performance Measures

Each model's performance has been evaluated employing four metrics: F1-score, recall, accuracy, and precision. These parameters given in below:

a. Confusion Matrix

Reputable academic performance metrics based on the confusion matrix were used to evaluate the outcomes. The matrix's visual is shown in Figure 3. The four main features of the matrix display the outcome data, while the matrix itself is an amalgamation of categorization results. A true positive (TP) result is one in which the actual value matches the anticipated value of the classification. A similar concept, known as a true negative (TN), centers around the number 0. The outcome is referred to as a false positive (FP) when the prediction is 1 and the real value is 0, while the converse is termed a false negative (FN).

		Actual Class Values	
		1	0
Predicted Class Values	1	True Positive (TP)	False Positive (FP)
	0	False Negative (FN)	True Negative (TN)

Figure 4: Representation class of confusion matrix

b. Accuracy

To get the accuracy rate, take all of the forecasts (including the actual predictions) and divide them by the entire number of predicted values. The corresponding equation is shown below:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FN + FP} \dots (6)$$

c. Precision

The precision metric is obtained by dividing the overall count of positive results by the overall count of negative results. The Precision metric is denoted, as shown below:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \dots (7)$$

d. Recall

Calculating recall is similar to calculating accuracy; it involves dividing the TP values by the TN values and the true positive values. The recall metric is expressed, as shown below:

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \dots (8)$$

E. F1-score

According to the F1 score, recall and precision are harmonically averaged. The F1 score is a popular evaluation tool in multi- and binary-class classification that integrates recall and precision into a single statistic to enhance understanding of the model's performance. the following expressed in words:

$$F1 - score = 2 * \frac{precision * recall}{precision + recall} \dots (9)$$

A. Experiment Results

The experiment results of the ML and DL models for Diagnosis of Leukemia and Blood Cancer are provided in this section. The outcomes are in a form of figures, graphs and tables.

Table 2: Performance of efficient Net V2S model on dataset

Measures	EfficientNetV2S
Accuracy	99.73
Precision	99.85
Recall	99.60
F1-score	99.72

Figure 5: Bar graph for EfficientNetV2S model performance

Bar graph for EfficientNetV2S model performance shows in figure 5. The EfficientNetV2S model shows outstanding performance in leukemia detection, with 99.73% accuracy, 99.85% precision, 99.60% recall, and a 99.72% F1-score, reflecting its high reliability and effectiveness across all metrics.

Figure 6: Accuracy graph of EfficientNetV2S model

Above figure 6 displays an Accuracy graph of an EfficientNetV2S model. Epoch 16 marked the end of the EfficientNetV2S model training, after three unsuccessful attempts to adjust the learning rate.

Figure 7: Loss graph of EfficientNetV2S model

The above figure 7 represents the Loss graph of EfficientNetV2S model. The loss curves try to combine with an ideal point as they gradually become smaller throughout training and validation. That there is no overfitting is shown by training and validation curves.

Figure 8: Confusion matrix of EfficientNetV2S Model

You can see the EfficientNetV2S Model's confusion matrix in Figure 8. Out of four thousand images, the EfficientNetV2S model identified only eleven that were misclassified, consisting of eight ALL images and three normal images.

B. Comparative Analysis

The comparative analysis for diagnosis of leukemia blood cancer based on deep learning. A following table displays a comparison among various DL and ML models for comparative analysis and diagnosis of leukemia blood cancer in terms of performance metrics.

Table 2: Comparison between various model for diagnosis of Leukemia Blood Cancer

Models	Accuracy	F1- score
NCA[10]	91.73	92.50
ResNet50[11]	82.83	82.84
EfficientNetV2S	99.73	99.72

Figure 9: Bar Graph for Accuracy comparison of models

Figure 9 above displays the Bar Graph for Model Accuracy Comparison. In this EfficientNetV2S has the highest accuracy score 99.73%, and RestNet50 has the lowest Accuracy with 82.83% score.

Figure 10: Comparison of F1-score performance of models

Figure 10 above displays the bar graph for the model F1-score comparison. In this figure, EfficientNetV2S has the highest F1-score 99.73%, and the RestNet50 has the lowest F1-score of 82.84%.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

Therefore, the analysis of this research demonstrates that through image of blood smears, deep learning and machine learning models are useful in detecting leukemia blood cancer. Data was first extracted from Kaggle platform from the C-NMC 2019 dataset and the subsequent preparation procedures included data augmentation for commonplace and image transformation to RGB models. For diagnosing leukemia blood cancer, a set of classification models was applied. These models included RestNet50, Neighborhood-Correction Algorithm and EfficientNetV2S. These include F1-score, recall, accuracy and precision that were used in assessing the performance of the model. Compared to other models, EfficientNetV2S demonstrated better 99.73% accuracy, 99.85% precision, 99.60% recall, and 99.72% F1-score, making it the highest-performing model in this comparative examination. Because they demonstrate the potential of such tools, our findings emphasize the possibility of using contemporary computational methodologies for the early identification and classification of life-threatening disorders like leukemia.

However, a number of drawbacks were found, including a limited dataset and challenges in rendering the models comprehensible. To get beyond these constraints, future research should focus on enhancing model designs, developing interpretability techniques, and investigating larger and more varied datasets. To improve the efficacy and precision of blood cancer leukemia detection in real-world clinical contexts, more trustworthy and clinically applicable diagnostic tools are required.

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